

1 **Inter-basin transfer megaprojects pose a decision dilemma under deeply uncertain futures:**
2 **the case of Godavari-Krishna water transfers in Southern India**

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10 **Highlights**

- 11 ● Identify candidate strategies to transfer water between monsoon dominated basins
- 12 ● Explore static as well as state-aware adaptive strategies to transfer water
- 13 ● Compare multi-objective performance under historical and future uncertainties
- 14 ● Adaptive strategies with coordinated information exchange show high performance
- 15 ● Strategy performance degrades with 10%-12% changes in long-term precipitation

16 **Abstract**

17 Globally, Inter-Basin Transfer (IBT) of water is being widely used to address water scarcity
18 concerns, with on-going and planned projects worth \$2.7 trillion. Water transfers must satisfy
19 diverse short-term and long-term preferences of donor and recipient basins, but the extent to

20 which IBT provides value under uncertain future water availability and demand is unclear. Here,
21 we identify and evaluate management strategies for a proposed IBT in Southern India; a vital
22 link in India's National River Linking Project (IRP).

23 We explore five ways to transfer water that distinguish static with adaptive strategies and explore
24 the role of information coordination between donor and recipient basins. Static (adaptive)
25 strategies prescribe transfer volumes independent of (dependent on) system states such as
26 reservoir levels. Static strategies include the status quo of no water transfer, a rule proposed by
27 regional authorities and an optimized rule. The two adaptive variants are adaptive-cooperative
28 and adaptive-noncooperative. Using a Many-Objective Robust Decision Making (MORDM)
29 approach, we identify strategies that trade-off between flood protection, demand satisfaction, and
30 environmental flow maintenance in the donor and recipient basins. We stress-test these
31 strategies under stochastically perturbed historical inflows, and deeply uncertain future climates
32 developed using a delta change approach. In the historical period, adaptive-cooperative strategies
33 show overall highest multi-objective performance, but their performance is significantly
34 degraded when long-term precipitation changes by 10% - 12%. The status quo of no water
35 transfer emerges as a viable alternative maintaining minimum performance under a large fraction
36 of deeply uncertain futures. Our analysis suggests the importance of a rigorous evaluation of
37 IBTs for better understanding of the relative benefits and management of such expensive
38 infrastructure.

39 **Keywords:** Interbasin transfer; India; optimization; many objective; dynamic rule; climate
40 change.

41

42 **1. Introduction**

43 Over the last two decades our estimates on the number of people living in water stressed
44 conditions across the globe have grown substantially (Arnell, 2004; Gosling and Arnell, 2016;
45 Kumm et al., 2010; Mekonnen and Hoekstra, 2016). Recently, Mekonnen and Hoekstra
46 (2016) estimated that 4 billion people live under conditions of severe water scarcity, from
47 which 1 billion reside in India alone. Climate and socio-economic changes are projected to
48 worsen the situation in South-east Asia posing a significant decision analytic challenge (Fant et
49 al., 2016; Fischer et al., 2007; Gosling and Arnell, 2016; Liu et al., 2017). Thus, there is an
50 immediate need to identify strategies to reduce water scarcity in impacted regions now while
51 avoiding decision lock-ins that limit adaptivity to deeply uncertain futures (Moallemi et al.,
52 2020; Walker et al., 2013).

53

54 Inter-basin transfer (IBT) of water is a widely discussed alternative for alleviating regional
55 differences in water scarcity (Vaux and Howitt, 1984; Ghassemi and White, 2007). A water
56 transfer project is considered as an IBT if volumetric transfers exceed $16 \text{ Mm}^3/\text{year}$ and transfer
57 infrastructures are longer than 20 km (Davies et al., 1992). Shumilova et al. (2018) further
58 identify IBT megaprojects as those with volumetric transfers exceeding $230 \text{ Mm}^3/\text{year}$ or
59 transfer infrastructures longer than 190 km. In this paper, the basin with water surplus and
60 deficit are termed as donor and recipient basins, respectively. The expected advantages of IBTs
61 include increased freshwater availability, hydropower generation, and flood management.
62 Overall, they are intended to improve the overall socio-economic development of the recipient
63 basin.

64

65 In 2005, IBTs represented ~14% of global water withdrawals which are estimated to increase to
66 48% in the future (Gupta and Van der Zaag, 2008; Shumilova et al., 2018). Shumilova et al.
67 (2018) present a global inventory of existing and future IBTs estimating transfer distance more
68 than two times of the Earth's equator due to future projects. Notable IBTs include China's
69 South-to-North IBT, South Africa's Lesotho Highlands project, California's state water project,
70 Australia's Snowy mountains scheme, etc. (Ghassemi and White,2007; Zhang et al. 2015;
71 Gichuki and McCornick, 2008; Shumilova et al., 2018).

72

73 IBTs have been studied using a variety of decision analytic approaches. These include game
74 theoretic methods considering a single objective function and multi-criteria decision making
75 methods that allow consideration of multiple planning objectives (Alahdin et al., 2018;
76 Jafarzadegan et al., 2014; Mahjouri et al., 2010; Ming et al.,2017; Shourian et al., 2017; Zhu et
77 al., 2014). Several analyses incorporate stochastic uncertainties while identifying optimal
78 transfer strategies (Jafarzadegan et al., 2013; Jafarzadegan et al., 2014). A few explore the
79 consequences of changing climate on IBTs (Chen and Xie, 2010; Maknoon et al., 2012) and the
80 role of cooperation between donor and recipient basins (Mahjouri et al., 2010; Manshadi et al.,
81 2015; Nikoo et al., 2012). Evolutionary algorithms have also been used, for example, to
82 identify optimal reservoir and tunnel capacity for an IBT in Iran (Shourian et al., 2017) and to
83 identify optimal operating rules for pumped storage of an IBT in China (Ming et al., 2017).
84 Another notable effort is the deterministic economic engineering optimization model for
85 California water transfers that identify water transfers while accounting for conjunctive use of
86 surface and groundwater (Draper et al., 2003; Lund et al., 2010).

87

88 IBTs require a careful balancing of water related goals for the donor and recipient basins,
89 including satisfying water demands, flood protection requirements, and environmental flow
90 requirements. Furthermore, IBT megaprojects require water managers to consider both near
91 term and long term consequences while evaluating their management options. The timing and
92 volume of transferred water can exacerbate flooding in monsoon-dominated regions, making
93 management crucial (Hall et al., 2014; Quinn et al., 2018). Management is particularly crucial
94 under uncertain future climate change and socio-economic change. It is also important to
95 rigorously evaluate the utility of large expensive capital infrastructure against the status quo
96 (i.e., no IBT) to avoid irreversible decision lock-ins. Thus, planning and operating IBT
97 megaprojects requires a framework that considers multiple (typically conflicting) objectives
98 and the consequences of uncertainties in drivers of water availability and demands (Yevjevich,
99 2001).

100

101 The complex decision context of IBTs necessitates an *a posteriori* decision framework that
102 allows decision makers to deliberately explore the tradeoffs and consequential vulnerabilities
103 that may emerge across different problem framing hypotheses (Herman et al., 2015; Kasprzyk
104 et al., 2013; Kwakkel and Haasnoot, 2019; Moallemi et al., 2020). Multiple, competing
105 hypotheses for how to frame these problems can aid in uncovering unintended consequences
106 that may not be apparent if only a single abstraction of the decision problem is explored (Quinn
107 et al., 2017a). Many-objective robust decision making (MORDM) provides an *a posteriori*
108 decision framework that allows for the discovery of tradeoffs between conflicting objectives for
109 donor and recipient basins (Kasprzyk et al., 2013; Singh et al., 2015). MORDM also provides a
110 mechanism for stress-testing operational alternatives under uncertain future climatic and/or

111 socio-economic changes. These long-term uncertainties, lacking a consensus on their
112 likelihoods and distributional forms, are termed “deep” or “Knightian” uncertainties (Knight,
113 1921; Lempert, 2002; Lempert et al., 2006). MORDM applications in socio-ecological systems
114 management (Eker and Kwakkel, 2018; Quinn et al., 2017b; Singh et al., 2015), water
115 resources management (Giuliani et al., 2015; Herman et al., 2014; Kasprzyk et al., 2013; Yan et
116 al., 2017), and urban water supply (Huskova et al., 2016; Trindade et al., 2019) suggest its
117 usefulness for a range of issues.

118

119 The National River Linking Project (NRLP) is one such IBT megaproject that intends to
120 transfer large volumes of water over great distances across the country. The project’s origins
121 are based on rapidly increasing water demands across the country, especially around urban
122 agglomerations. In this study, we use MORDM to discover and evaluate alternative operational
123 strategies for the Inchampalli-Nagarjuna Sagar (INS) IBT megaproject in Southern India. The
124 INS IBT is likely to affect approximately 20 million people, predominantly farmers. It is also
125 an important link within the NRLP. Thus, assessing its viability under deeply uncertain futures
126 will pave the way for replicating such analyses in other parts of India. Using multiple framings
127 of the IBT decision problem, we address three important questions.

- 128 1. Is the INS IBT a better alternative to the status quo of no water transfer?
- 129 2. How do adaptive state-aware strategies facilitating inter-basin information coordination
130 compare to the strategy prescribed by regional authorities?
- 131 3. Does the IBT maintain its performance under long-term changes in climate and socio-
132 economic conditions in the donor and recipient basins?

133

134 **2. Case Study: Inchampalli-Nagarjuna Sagar Link in South India**

135 The implications of large spatio-temporal distribution of rainfall are of particular concern to
136 India. Around 75-90% of rainfall occurs between June and September indicating a strong rainfall
137 seasonality (Parthasarathy et al., 1988; Dhanya and Kumar, 2009). Also, low per capita water
138 storage affects water scarcity, being only 200 m³/person compared to roughly 6000 m³/person in
139 the USA (Briscoe and Malik, 2006). Conflicting goals of different stakeholders and water
140 scarcity poses water management challenges in India (Reddy and Kumar, 2009). The NRLP aims
141 to connect 44 rivers via 30 water transfers to improve food security and increase fresh water
142 availability (Bagla, 2014; Bharati et al., 2008; Joshi, 2013; NCIWRD, 1999). Nearly half (16) of
143 these are located in peninsular India.

144

145 The Godavari and Krishna are the largest river basins in peninsular India, together covering 18%
146 of the area of India and spanning multiple states (sub-national administrative units) (Figure 1a).
147 Agriculture dominates land use in these basins, with the donor Godavari basin having large areas
148 under forest cover (Figure 1b). Historically, the Godavari river maintains much higher flow
149 volumes than the Krishna river. The Krishna basin has witnessed rapid upstream development
150 that has led to the construction of several dams and reduced water availability in downstream
151 regions (Gaur et al., 2008; George et al., 2011; Venot et al., 2010). Three projects are proposed
152 to transfer water from the Godavari to the Krishna river basin (Figure 1b). This study focuses on
153 the INS IBT, the largest of the three and located upstream of the other two. Details on the donor
154 and recipient basins for the INS IBT are provided in Table 1.

155

156 Historical values of irrigation demands were calculated for both basins by assuming an annually
157 fixed cropping pattern and estimating the net requirements for each crop (Prasad et al. 2006,
158 Supplementary Material S1). Demands peak in the monsoon period when water intensive crops
159 are cultivated, reducing thereafter and remaining at a minimum during the summer periods
160 (Figure S1). Irrigation demands form a major component of demands in either basins, 85%
161 (100%) for the recipient (donor) reservoir. Domestic demands are calculated using population
162 data and per capita demand value (NWDA, 2020). Industrial demands are assumed to be equal to
163 domestic demands. Historical estimates show that the donor basin maintains a great water
164 surplus with annual water availability far exceeding the demands. On the other hand, the
165 recipient basin maintains a relatively small margin between its supply and demands, even at
166 annual time scales. Additionally, the recipient reservoir is a major source of water for Hyderabad
167 city, a major metropolitan city in India.

168

169 The volumes of proposed water transfers and the distance through which they will travel classify
170 the INS IBT as a megaproject (Shumilova et al., 2018). Around 16,426 Mm³ of water is proposed
171 to be transferred from the donor to the recipient basin via a 299 Km canal (Jain et al., 2007;
172 NWDA, 2020). The water transfer is intended to be multi-purpose by supporting irrigation,
173 domestic, and industrial water uses in the recipient basin. The feasibility report by the National
174 Water Development Authority (NWDA) provides a comparative baseline operating schedule for
175 the water transfer, termed as the *proposed* transfer in the rest of the study (NWDA, 2020). The
176 feasibility report estimates annual inflows at each site through a water balance analysis

177 accounting for climate, upstream demands, and upstream imports or exports of water. From this,
178 reservoir yields were calculated as annual flow values with 75% exceedance probability using a
179 flow duration curve for the period 1950-1980. The annual water transfer volume is determined
180 by comparing the reservoir yields with demands in the donor and recipient basins. The seasonal
181 distribution of the transfer is estimated using a water balance analysis that considers inflows and
182 demands at monthly time scales.

183

184 The recipient Nagarjuna Sagar reservoir is also envisioned to support additional water transfers
185 to satisfy domestic and agriculture demands in regions further south of the recipient basin via the
186 proposed Nagarjuna Sagar – Somasila transfer. This requirement is abstracted in the decision
187 problem as a predefined water transfer demand which is satisfied by reservoir releases but is not
188 a decision variable. Similarly, the volume of water proposed to be allocated from the donor
189 reservoir to other basins is treated as a predefined abstraction. The annual volumes of predefined
190 transfers for the donor and recipient are 4,370 Mm³ and 14,200 Mm³, respectively (NWDA,
191 2020). Notably, these volumes are much larger than the local demands on both the reservoirs.

192

193 Inflow data for the donor reservoir at the Perur gage station is obtained from the Central Water
194 Commission for the time period of 1967-2012. For the recipient reservoir, inflow to the existing
195 Nagarjuna Sagar dam for the time period of 1967-2016 is obtained from the Irrigation and CAD
196 Department, Telangana. Climate data comprising of daily precipitation and temperature is
197 obtained from the Indian Meteorological Department (IMD), Pune. Daily precipitation data is
198 available at a spatial resolution of 0.25×0.25° from 1901-2013. Daily minimum, maximum and

199 mean temperature data is available at a spatial resolution of $1 \times 1^\circ$ for the years 1951-2013. The
200 aggregated climate time series data was estimated for both donor and recipient basins based on
201 area-averaging. Potential evapotranspiration is estimated from temperature time series using the
202 Hargreaves equation (Hargreaves and Samani, 1985).

203

204 **3. Methodology**

205 We identify and evaluate different operational transfer strategies for the INS project using the
206 MORDM framework as illustrated in Figure 2. Section 3.1 describes the competing problem
207 formulation hypotheses. Then the IBT model is described in Section 3.2 followed by a discussion
208 on methods for incorporating uncertainties in the analysis in Section 3.3. We then describe the
209 objective functions in Section 3.4. Section 3.5 discusses stochastic multi-objective evolutionary
210 search algorithm to identify candidate operational strategies and their performance tradeoffs
211 under historically observed uncertainties. We conclude this section with a description of the
212 robustness analysis used in this study to evaluate the performance of candidate transfer strategies
213 under deep uncertainties in section 3.6.

214

215 **3.1 Problem framing hypotheses for the inter-basin transfer**

216 There are four main components to any decision problem: decision variables, performance
217 measures that quantify the stakeholders' objectives, a model that maps decisions to objectives'
218 performance, and exogenous uncertainties (Lempert, 2003). Problem formulation is a critical
219 step in the MORDM framework (Kasprzyk et al., 2009; Zeff et al., 2014). Exploring rival
220 candidate framings of a decision problem helps the decision makers to understand how

221 vulnerabilities are shaped by changes in representations of decisions or assumptions, especially
222 for complex decision contexts like the INS project (Quinn et al., 2017a). The decision variables
223 in the INS IBT problem are the volumes of water to be transferred each month. In our analysis,
224 we explore five ways to specify these transfers, constituting five different problem framing
225 hypothesis (Table 2). Our rival framings specifically distinguish a static (“open loop control”)
226 operational rule used by the regional authorities to initially evaluate the INS IBT versus a state-
227 aware adaptive rule that facilitates broader information sharing between donor and recipient
228 reservoirs (“closed loop control”, Quinn et al., 2017b). Open loop strategies prescribe each
229 decision in a time series as an independent decision and optimize them simultaneously. Thus, a
230 vector of decision variables, θ is specified as:

$$231 \quad \theta = (\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_{12}) \quad \theta_i \in [0, 2800] \quad (1)$$

232 Where, 2800 Mm³ is the capacity of the proposed canal that will transfer water.

233

234 **3.1.1. Adaptive formulations**

235 Closed loop control (or adaptive) strategies specify decisions conditioned on system state
236 variables (Giuliani et al., 2015; Quinn et al., 2017a; Salazar et al., 2017). Two versions are
237 explored in this study to distinguish the value of information sharing between the donor and
238 recipient reservoirs (i.e., operational coordination). Our adaptive formulation is based on direct
239 policy search (DPS) wherein the rule form for operational strategies are approximated as
240 nonlinear functions that vary with certain parameters and system states (Giuliani et al., 2015;
241 Salazar et al., 2017). Building off of prior published recommendations, we have adopted radial
242 basis functions (RBF) to formulate state-aware water transfer policies (Giuliani et al., 2015). At

243 each time step, the volume of water to be transferred, tr_t in an adaptive-cooperative strategy is
 244 estimated as a function of reservoir storage volumes based on the inflow and demands in either
 245 basin (Equation 2).

246

$$247 \quad tr_t = \begin{cases} \exp\left(-\sum_{j=1}^2 \frac{((x_t)_j - c_{j,1})^2}{b_{j,1}^2}\right) \text{ if } q_t^D, q_t^R \in [0, 3000) \text{ and } d_t^D, d_t^R \in [0, 500) & \text{(RBF1)} \\ \exp\left(-\sum_{j=1}^2 \frac{((x_t)_j - c_{j,2})^2}{b_{j,2}^2}\right) \text{ if } q_t^D, q_t^R \in [3000, 18000) \text{ and } d_t^D, d_t^R \in [700, \infty) & \text{(RBF2)} \\ \exp\left(-\sum_{j=1}^2 \frac{((x_t)_j - c_{j,3})^2}{b_{j,3}^2}\right) \text{ otherwise.} & \text{(RBF3)} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

248 $(x_t)_1$ and $(x_t)_2$ are the donor reservoir and recipient storage volumes, respectively. The variables
 249 q and d represent inflow and demands (in Mm^3), respectively. The subscript t refers to the time
 250 step. The superscripts D and R represent the donor (D) and recipient (R) basins' fluxes. The
 251 variables c and b are the parameters of the radial basis function. Inflow and demand ranges
 252 represent three conditions that are likely to exist in donor and recipient reservoirs: low inflows
 253 with moderate demands (RBF1), moderate inflows with high demands (RBF2), and all other
 254 conditions (RBF3). RBF3 accounts for other possible combinations of inflow and demands such
 255 as low flows with high demands, high flows and high demands, etc. The decision variables are
 256 the parameters of the RBF policies. The three RBFs (Equation 2) each have four parameters,
 257 resulting in 12 overall decision variables for a fully specified transfer policy function (Equation
 258 3).

259

$$\theta = \begin{bmatrix} c_{i,j} \\ b_{i,j} \end{bmatrix} \text{ with } i = \{1, \dots, 3\}, j = \{1, \dots, 2\} \quad (3)$$

260 where $c_{i,j} \in [-1,1]$ and $b_{i,j} \in [0,1]$.

261 The adaptive-noncooperative formulation conditions water transfers only on the storage level of
262 the donor reservoir. This formulation is used to assess the role of real-time information exchange
263 between donor and recipient basins in obtaining better performance of water transfer strategies.
264 The formulation comprises of 6 decision variables (Equation 4).

$$265 \quad \theta = \begin{bmatrix} c_{i,j} \\ b_{i,j} \end{bmatrix} \text{ with } i = \{1, \dots, 3\}, j = \{1\} \quad (4)$$

266

267 **3.2 IBT Model**

268 The IBT model simulates the water balance of the donor and recipient reservoirs, which are
269 linked by the water transfer canal (Figure 1a). We estimate the volume of storage in the
270 reservoirs at the end of time step t for donor and recipient reservoirs based on equations 5 and 6:

$$271 \quad s_t^D = s_{t-1}^D + q_t^D - ef_t^D - pt_t^D - tr_t - d_t^D - r_t^D \quad (5)$$

$$272 \quad s_t^R = s_{t-1}^R + q_t^R - ef_t^R - pt_t^R + tr_t - d_t^R - r_t^R \quad (6)$$

273 where s is the volume of storage, q is the inflow, ef is the minimum environmental flow
274 releases downstream, pt represents predefined transfers, tr is volume of water transferred
275 from donor to recipient reservoir, and d is water released for satisfying demand (aggregate
276 value of domestic, industrial and agricultural demands). Subscript t refers to the time step and

277 superscripts refer to donor (D) and recipient (R) reservoir fluxes. As described in section 2,
278 predefined transfers quantify prior commitment to release water for other water transfers. This
279 flux is essential as the same reservoir may transfer water to more than one reservoir in another
280 basin. If the water level in either reservoir exceeds 95% of active capacity once water is released
281 for demand satisfaction, the excess water is released downstream, these releases are denoted by
282 r . As several fluxes remove water from the reservoir, it is possible that their sum is more than
283 the total available water at any time step. This necessitates prioritizing release decisions. The
284 order of releases is incorporated in the model based on personal communications with the
285 reservoir operators, who suggested that commitments related to water transfers are given a
286 priority when compared to satisfying demands (i.e., domestic, industrial and agricultural).
287 Additionally, we prioritize environmental flows to maintain ecological balance downstream of
288 both reservoirs to minimize the effect on ecosystem due to transfers. Based on these
289 considerations, releases are ordered as follows: minimum environmental flows, predefined
290 transfers, water transfer from donor to recipient reservoir, and demand satisfaction. The model
291 simulates various fluxes using a fortnightly (15-day) time step.

292

293 **3.3 Uncertainty analysis**

294 In this study, we distinguish between two types of uncertainties that shape the consequences of
295 reservoir operations: (1) well-characterized stationary stochastic hydro-climatic variability in
296 stream flows and (2) long-term non-stationary deep uncertainties associated with climate and/or
297 socio-economic changes. Recall that the *proposed* strategy was identified using an approach that
298 is based on deterministic historical observations, neglecting the internal variability of inflows as

299 well as possible changes in future climate and demands. Our goal here is to analyze strategies
300 against this comparative baseline and the status quo where the IBT is absent. We know that the
301 historical streamflow observation record is a limited single realization from a complex stochastic
302 process that underestimates internal variability as well as increasingly rare flood or drought
303 extremes. Stationary stochastic streamflow generation provides a means to exploit historical
304 streamflow observations to build a better ensemble representation of the variability that could
305 confront major infrastructure operations such as the water transfers analyzed here (Hao and
306 Singh, 2016). Beyond stationary statistical assessments, long-term changes in climate (and
307 consequently inflows) and socio-economic factors pose non-stationary changes in the system that
308 are deeply uncertain (Langlios and Cosgel, 1993; Lempert, 2002; Lempert, 2003).

309

310 We quantify the stochastic uncertainty in reservoir inflows by using a bootstrapping sampling
311 technique developed by Kirsch et al. (2012). Using Cholesky decomposition to maintain
312 autocorrelation and bootstrap resampling to preserve multisite correlation, we generate 10,000
313 realizations of inflow time series for 15 years using 45 years of historical data (Figure 2b;
314 Herman et al., 2016; Kirsch et al., 2012). The 15-year period is selected as a likely planning
315 horizon for reservoir operators. For more details on the generator refer to supplementary material
316 S2. Deep uncertainties related to long-term changes in climate and demand are explored by
317 generating scenarios for both donor and recipient basins. Climate scenarios are generated by
318 using the delta change method that alters historically observed precipitation and temperature time
319 series by a constant value. Thus, the mean values of climate variables are altered while
320 preserving higher order statistics. The delta change method is chosen for its simplicity though it
321 has limitations in estimating extremes (Brunner et al., 2018). We believe that this approach

322 would provide a preliminary assessment of strategy performance under a changing climate and
323 future studies should focus on methods to include uncertainties in seasonality of inflows.

324

325 The ranges for probable future climate change are obtained from prior literature and analysis of
326 climate projections from climate models (IPCC, 2013; Kumar et al., 2006; Warszawski et
327 al.,2014). We assess the change in mean annual precipitation and temperature from a reference
328 period of 1986-2005 to end-of-century using climate projections from 42 climate models for four
329 representative concentration pathways (RCPs): RCP 2.6, RCP 4.5, RCP 6.0, and RCP 8.5
330 scenarios. We further corroborated the ranges thus obtained with the climate projection data
331 available from the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISI-MIP, Warszawski
332 et al.,2014). Thus, precipitation changes are sampled from -30% to 50% of historical mean
333 annual precipitation and temperature increases are sampled from 0°C to 5°C of historical mean
334 annual temperature. By generating a large number of climates encompassing these ranges, we are
335 able to identify the safe operating space for the INS IBT (Gold et al., 2019).

336

337 As climate models predict similar changes in precipitation and temperature for the donor and
338 recipient basins, the change is simultaneously applied to both. Total water demands are assumed
339 to increase from 0% to 50% in both the basins. In this way, a total of 10,000 climate and demand
340 scenarios (or SOWs, Lempert et al., 2006) are generated by combining changes in precipitation,
341 temperature, and demands in donor and recipient basins using Latin hypercube sampling
342 (McKay et al., 1979). To simulate reservoir inflows under different climates, the Probability

343 Distribution Model (PDM) is used. See supplementary text S3 for details on model and model
344 calibration.

345

346 **3.4 Performance measures**

347 The prefeasibility assessments used to design the *proposed* strategy mainly focused on demand
348 satisfaction. However, we consider two additional objectives that are likely to be important in
349 monsoon dominated regions: flood protection and maintenance of minimum environmental
350 flows. The recipient reservoir has witnessed few floods during its historical operation- three
351 major floods between 1969 and 2013 (EPTRI, 2008; Killada et al., 2012). Due to this, flood
352 protection is not yet considered as an important function of the reservoir. However, our analysis
353 of future climate data revealed several scenarios where increases in both mean annual
354 precipitation and monsoonal precipitation are possible. Therefore, we included flood protection
355 as a primary objective in our analysis. In addition, maintenance of minimum environmental
356 flows is likely to become a concern if water transfers start affecting downstream biota.
357 Downstream of the proposed reservoir, there are communities that derive their livelihood from
358 the river itself and will be negatively affected once minimum environmental requirements are not
359 met (Sharma et al., 2008; Smakhtin, 2006).

360

361 Reliability, resilience, and vulnerability are routinely used to evaluate a candidate design's
362 success (Hashimoto et al., 1982; Zhang et al., 2017). Reliability is defined as the probability that
363 the system is in a satisfactory state, i.e., when available supply satisfies the demands (Fowler et
364 al., 2003; Hashimoto et al., 1982; Mondal and Wasimi, 2007). Resilience quantifies how quickly

365 a system recovers from failure states. Vulnerability quantifies the magnitude of failure, in this
366 case being the average demand deficit. In this way we define five objectives to evaluate the
367 performance of water transfer strategies: reliability, vulnerability and resilience of demand
368 satisfaction, reliability of flood protection, and reliability in maintaining minimum environmental
369 flows (Table 3). Three objective functions related to demand satisfaction are included as the
370 primary purpose of the water transfer is to satisfy demands and prior literature has shown the
371 existence of tradeoff among the three metrics of reliability, resilience and vulnerability
372 (Hashimoto et al., 1982; Zhang et al., 2017).

373

374 Reliability related objectives are expressed as percentage and demand vulnerability is expressed
375 as average demand deficits in million cubic meters. Resilience is the average duration taken to
376 recover from failure, expressed in multiples of 15 days. Minimum environmental flows to be
377 released downstream are set at 30% of the mean historical flow (Smakhtin, 2006). The flood
378 thresholds to define failure states for flood reliability are derived from historical data of
379 downstream releases (for more details on defining flood thresholds refer supplementary material
380 S4). In addition to these objective functions, the transfer strategies are also required to maintain a
381 minimum performance for the reliability of maintaining minimum environmental flows and
382 reliability of meeting pre-defined transfers goals (constraints in Table 3).

383

384 **3.5 Generating alternatives using evolutionary multi-objective search**

385 The optimal transfer strategies for the static, adaptive-cooperative, and adaptive-noncooperative
386 problem formulations are found by generating the non-dominated set of decision variable

387 vectors, θ^* , that minimize the vector of objectives, $J(\theta)$, subject to two constraints (Equations
 388 7, 8, 9).

$$389 \quad \theta^* = \operatorname{argmin}_{\theta} J(\theta), \quad (7)$$

390 where

$$391 \quad J(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} -(J_{rel}^D(\theta) + J_{rel}^R(\theta)) / 2 \\ (J_{res}^D(\theta) + J_{res}^R(\theta)) / 2 \\ (J_{vul}^D(\theta) + J_{vul}^R(\theta)) / 2 \\ -(J_{flood}^D(\theta) + J_{flood}^R(\theta)) / 2 \\ -(J_{EF}^D(\theta) + J_{EF}^R(\theta)) / 2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

392 Subject to

393

$$394 \quad \begin{aligned} J_{PT}(\theta) &\leq 0.75 \\ J_{EF}(\theta) &\leq 0.75 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

395 Here, superscripts denote the objective function value for the donor (D) and recipient (R)
 396 reservoirs. The subscripts denote different objective functions as defined in Table 3. We use a
 397 multi-objective evolutionary algorithm, the Borg MOEA, to search the space of decision
 398 variables and identify Pareto optimal water transfer strategies (Hadka and Reed, 2013). Recent
 399 studies show that the Borg MOEA provides competitive to superior results compared to other
 400 MOEAs on test problems and also real-world water resource problems (Hadka and Reed 2012;
 401 Reed et al., 2013; Salazar et al., 2016; Ward et al., 2015). We apply a stochastic multi-objective
 402 search that uses a random sample of 100 (out of 10,000) realizations of inflow time series to

403 estimate $J(\theta)$ for each function evaluation of the Borg MOEA. An aggregated measure of
404 objective function values across the uncertain inflow ensemble is calculated. Here, we aggregate
405 the objective functions by estimating their mean value assuming a risk neutral formulation, a
406 commonly used approach in water resources problems (Labadie, 2004; Quinn et al., 2017a). The
407 number of realizations used for each BORG function evaluation is chosen to reduce the
408 computational demands. The attained solutions were re-evaluated against a much larger and
409 independent set of 100,000 realizations of inflow time series. Further details on setting up the
410 BORG MOEA related to epsilon settings for each objective function, parameterization of the
411 algorithm and the choice of parallelization scheme are provided in supplementary material S5.

412

413 **3.6 Robustness analysis**

414 The INS IBT will likely engender potentially rapid transformation in socio-economic
415 development in both basins triggered in part possibly by its own presence, as well as significant
416 changes in climate and non-climate factors. These changes are likely to be deeply uncertain, i.e.,
417 they cannot be quantified using probabilistic approaches. Therefore, we perform a robustness
418 analysis to test strategy performance across a large number of deeply uncertain climate and water
419 demand scenarios. Robustness measures the ability of a strategy to maintain performance when
420 the operational reality departs from the assumed conditions under which the stochastic
421 optimization was performed. The methodology used to identify transfer volumes in the
422 feasibility report by regional authorities suggests a strong focus on demand satisfaction at annual
423 or coarser time scales. Therefore, a minimum performance threshold for vulnerability of demand
424 satisfaction (or the average demand deficit) is specified. We further included minimum

425 performance thresholds for reliability of preventing downstream flooding and maintaining
426 minimum environmental flows. This decision was made based on the rationale that flood and
427 minimum environmental flow related requirements may become important in the future when
428 climate departs from the historical observations and negative downstream impacts of the water
429 transfers begin to surface. Finally, an additional requirement of maintaining annual transfer
430 volumes below 50% of the annual volume in the *proposed* strategy is imposed. A significant
431 amount of literature points to potential ecological damages by large scale IBTs and minimizing
432 the transfer volumes provides one way to reduce such impacts (Grant et al., 2012).

433

434 We set the performance thresholds for each performance measure after assessing the multi-
435 objective performance of strategies under stochastic uncertainty. Given the complexity of the
436 INS IBT as well as the diversity of potential stakeholder interests, a standard stakeholder
437 elicitation of the required performance requirements and thresholds for defining robustness is not
438 straight forward. The implications of choosing the thresholds are not easily inferred or reflective
439 of a consensus on known requirements. Therefore, we present in this study an *a posteriori*
440 sensitivity analysis that allows regional stakeholders to assess whether our evaluations of system
441 robustness change widely for a range of candidate satisficing performance thresholds. The list of
442 performance measures considered for evaluating robustness and the ranges explored for the
443 sensitivity analysis are presented in Table 4.

444

445 Here, robustness is calculated using satisficing criteria, as the percentage of SOWs in which a
446 strategy satisfies pre-defined performance thresholds (Herman et al., 2015, Equation 10).

447

$$\% \text{ robust} = \frac{1}{N_{SOW}} \times \left(\sum_{j=1}^{N_{SOW}} S_{k,j} \right) \times 100 \quad (10)$$

448

449 where $S_{k,j} = 1$ if strategy k meets the robustness condition for SOW j and $S_{k,j} = 0$ otherwise.

450 Note also that robustness is estimated by applying the performance requirements on both donor

451 and recipient basins simultaneously, as well as for each basin individually. For comparison

452 purposes, robustness is estimated under both stochastic and deep uncertainties. The robustness

453 estimates thus obtained across 10,000 SOWs are further analyzed using Classification and

454 Regression Trees (CART) to identify the relative importance of deeply uncertain factors

455 (Supplementary material S6).

456

457 **4. Results**

458 **4.1 Optimal water transfer strategies under stochastic uncertainties**

459 We find substantial tradeoffs in the performance of objective functions across transfer strategies

460 obtained from the stochastic multi-objective optimization (Figure 3). We compare the *proposed*

461 strategy (grey pentagons) against the three Pareto approximate sets discovered through the *static*

462 (green), *adaptive-cooperative* (blue) and *adaptive-noncooperative* (red) problem formulations.

463 Overall we obtained 167 alternative transfer strategies after optimization, 46 (79, 42) of which

464 were obtained by *static* (*adaptive-cooperative*, *adaptive-noncooperative*) formulations. The

465 range of objective function values across all strategies are 89%-93%, 37-69 days, 14 Mm³-27

466 Mm³, 97%-98%, and 97%-98%, for reliability and resilience of demand satisfaction, average

467 demand deficits, reliability of flood protection, and reliability of maintaining minimum
468 environmental flows, respectively. Recall that resilience quantifies the time taken by the system
469 to recover from failures. Also, the vulnerability objective is directly proportional to average
470 demand deficits, thus average demand deficits are presented to facilitate interpretation of the
471 results. The *no-transfer* strategy that assumes that the donor and recipient basins manage their
472 water resources independently is also shown in the figure (black stars). Figure 3a visualizes three
473 objectives: the reliability and resilience of demand satisfaction, and average demand deficit. As
474 demand satisfaction is of primary concern to regional authorities, the performance across these
475 three objectives is discussed first. Each objective is represented on an axis in the figure, the black
476 cross marking the ideal solution which simultaneously optimizes all objectives. Due to conflicts
477 between the objectives, the ideal solution is not achievable for any problem formulation.

478

479 Strategies discovered through multi-objective search strongly outperform the *no-transfer* and
480 *proposed* strategies across the three demand satisfaction measures averaged across both basins
481 (Figure 3a). The *proposed* strategy attained the lowest performance in all objectives except
482 average demand deficits for which it obtained a value of 15 Mm³. The average demand deficits
483 attained by *static* (*adaptive-cooperative*, *adaptive-noncooperative*) strategies range from 14-27
484 Mm³ (14-24 Mm³, 14-24 Mm³). This suggests that the *proposed* strategy is biased toward
485 minimizing average demand deficits at annual or coarser time scales. This, however, does not
486 translate to higher performance in terms of the frequency of avoiding demand deficits
487 (reliability) or the ability to recover from demand deficits (resilience). It is possible to identify
488 strategies that are better in all three measures of demand satisfaction using stochastic multi-
489 objective optimization. The *proposed* and *no-transfer* strategies obtain a demand satisfaction

490 reliability of 85% and 77%, respectively, whereas the *static* (*adaptive-cooperative*, *adaptive-*
491 *noncooperative*) strategies attain a minimum value of 89% (90%, 91%).

492

493 The *adaptive-noncooperative* strategies are dominated by the *adaptive-cooperative* strategies
494 (i.e., perform worse in all objectives), highlighting the value of coordinating information
495 exchange between donor and recipient basins. The *adaptive-cooperative* and *static* strategies
496 attain better values of resilience of demand satisfaction, due to which they are located closer to
497 the ideal solution. The mean values for resilience of demand satisfaction across all strategies for
498 the *adaptive-cooperative* (*static*, *adaptive-noncooperative*) formulation is 45 days (45 days, 55
499 days). Thus, *adaptive-noncooperative* strategies take more time to recover from failure.

500 However, different problem framings attain nearly the same performance for the reliability of
501 demand satisfaction for which the mean objective function value is 92% (92%, 92%) for the
502 *adaptive-cooperative* (*static*, *adaptive-noncooperative*) formulation. Due to its inferior multi-
503 objective performance, we assume that we have falsified the *adaptive-noncooperative*
504 formulation and focus only on the *static* and *adaptive-cooperative* problem framings from
505 hereon.

506

507 We find that the ability to recover from deficits is inversely related to average demand deficits.
508 This is evident by the tradeoffs between demand resilience and average demand deficits for the
509 optimized strategies. The relationship between resilience, reliability, and average deficits of
510 demand satisfaction obtained here are in agreement with from prior literature on risk based water
511 management (Bayazit and Unal, 1990; Hashimoto et al., 1982; Moy et al., 1986; Zhang et al.,

512 2017). A metric-based assessment of the quality of our search results is provided for the three
513 multi-objective formulations in Figure S4 of the supplementary information.

514

515 A key advantage of the *adaptive-cooperative* strategies is that they are able to obtain high
516 performance levels across all objectives while maintaining relatively low volumes of water
517 transferred (Figure 3b). Figure 3b shows the performance of the *static* (green lines) and *adaptive-*
518 *cooperative* (blue lines) strategies across all five objectives. Each objective is represented by a
519 vertical axis, oriented such that preferred values are at the top. Each transfer strategy plots as a
520 line on the graph. An ideal solution would be represented as a horizontal line crossing each
521 vertical axis at the top. Tradeoffs between objectives are indicated by lines representing different
522 strategies crossing each other diagonally. The transparency level of the lines indicates the
523 volume of annual transfers entailed by a strategy. The figure shows that most of the adaptive-
524 cooperative strategies entail lower volumetric transfers. Furthermore, the *no-transfer* strategy
525 (plotted as stars) outperforms all others in the reliability of flood protection, averaged across both
526 basins. Thus, in absence of the INS IBT, both basins will be able to maintain downstream
527 releases below historically observed values for the vast majority of time periods. However, the
528 overall narrow range of the objective function value indicates that these tradeoffs are not likely
529 significant and it is possible to manage floods while achieving much higher benefits for demand
530 satisfaction across both basins.

531

532 We also observe multi-actor tradeoffs across objective functions on reevaluating the performance
533 of transfer strategies for the donor and recipient basins individually (Figure 3c). As expected, the

534 *no-transfer* strategy favors the donor basin for the reliability and resilience of demand
535 satisfaction as well as the reliability of maintaining minimum environmental flows. However,
536 even for the donor basin the *no-transfer* strategy performs worse than the optimized strategies for
537 average demand deficits and the reliability of flood protection. This deterioration in performance
538 of the *no-transfer* strategy for average demand deficits can be attributed to the presence of
539 stochastic uncertainties. The optimized strategies are able to improve their performance by
540 considering stochastic stationary uncertainties during the optimization which the deterministic
541 *no-transfer* strategy does not.

542

543 The *proposed* strategy has better performance in the recipient basin compared to donor basin for
544 reliability of demand satisfaction and average demand deficits as well as the reliability of
545 maintaining minimum environmental flows. The difference between average demand deficits for
546 the donor and recipient basins is quite small for the *proposed* strategy. This indicates that the
547 regional authorities initial design is strongly concerned with balancing the deficits across both
548 basins. Such tradeoffs between achievable performance between donor and recipient basins also
549 exist for the *static* and *adaptive-cooperative* strategies. Of note is the conflict between reliability
550 of demand satisfaction in donor and recipient basins for *adaptive-cooperative* strategies.
551 *Adaptive-cooperative (static)* strategies attain a reliability of demand satisfaction value in the
552 range 91% - 96% (89% - 95%) for the donor basin and 86% - 92% (88% - 92%) for the recipient
553 basin. Although the difference in performance of this objective between the *static* and *adaptive-*
554 *cooperative* strategies is not significant, *adaptive-cooperative* strategies attain the same
555 performance for much lower volumetric transfers as discussed earlier.

556

557 A key advantage of the *adaptive-cooperative* strategies is that they are able to obtain high
558 performance levels across all objectives while maintaining relatively low volumes of water
559 transferred (Figure 4). The mean value of annual transfer volumes across all strategies and time
560 periods is 6460 Mm³ (9194 Mm³) for the *adaptive-cooperative (static)* formulations,
561 respectively. The *proposed* strategy suggests a much higher volume of annual transfers, 13,434
562 Mm³. Furthermore, the *proposed* strategy transfers most of the water during the monsoon season
563 (July-Oct) but other strategies avoid water transfer in late monsoon (Aug-Oct). This is likely due
564 to explicit inclusion of flood related objectives in the optimization. Lower transfer volumes
565 reduce the cost of construction and maintenance of infrastructure and also have less
566 environmental impacts, so *adaptive-cooperative* strategies present a distinct advantage over
567 others, even under stochastic uncertainties.

568

569 **4.2 Strategy performance under deeply uncertain climate and demands**

570 As the INS IBT is a large scale project with a long life time, it is imperative that its
571 performance remains acceptable under deeply uncertain futures. We therefore test the
572 performance of strategies obtained from the *static* and *adaptive-cooperative* formulations
573 under changes in climate and demands using a satisficing robustness measure considering
574 four criteria (Table 4). Although the minimum performance thresholds used to estimate
575 robustness values are generally elicited from decision makers, we assume that decision
576 makers' preference are reflected in the multi-objective performance attained from stochastic
577 optimization. The average attainable objective function values across all strategies under

578 stochastic uncertainties is 20 Mm³, 97%, and 97% for average demand deficits, reliability of
579 flood protection and reliability of maintaining minimum environmental flows, respectively.
580 These are used as minimum performance thresholds. We impose an additional requirement
581 of keeping the annual volumes of water transferred below 50% those suggested by the
582 *proposed* strategy. This requirement reflects ecological concerns related to large scale water
583 transfers that are known to affect water quality, flora and fauna in the recipient regions
584 (Grant et al., 2012; Zhuang, 2016). We evaluate the robustness measure in three ways
585 depending upon whether the performance requirements have to be met for both donor and
586 recipient reservoir simultaneously, only for the donor reservoir, or only for the recipient
587 reservoir.

588

589 Under stochastic stationary uncertainties, the *adaptive-cooperative* strategies attain greater
590 robustness when compared to *static* strategies if both donor and recipient reservoirs are
591 considered simultaneously (Figure 5a-c). The *proposed* and *no-transfer* strategies cannot
592 maintain performance requirements (0% and 10% robustness) when considering both donor
593 and recipient reservoirs. The *adaptive-cooperative* strategies are able to attain robustness
594 values up to 45% under stochastic uncertainties. The *proposed* strategy attains 0% (35%)
595 robustness when considering only the donor (recipient) reservoir (Figures 5b,c). These
596 results highlight the importance of cooperative coordination between the basins and using
597 adaptive state-aware strategies in managing water transfers.

598

599 Transitioning to deeply uncertain futures, we find a reduction in robustness as future climate
600 and demand conditions depart from historical observations (Figures 5d-f). As in the case of
601 stochastic uncertainties, the robustness of the *proposed* strategy is 0% considering both
602 donor and recipient reservoirs simultaneously. The *adaptive-cooperative* strategies maintain
603 minimum performance requirements in 18%-30% deeply uncertain states-of-the-world. This
604 reduction in robustness is attributed to different failure modes of strategies optimized over
605 historical uncertainties. Increases in long-term precipitation may lead to failure in the flood
606 related objective when using historically optimized strategies. Conversely, reductions in
607 long-term precipitation would require too large volumetric transfers to reduce demand
608 deficits, leading to violation of the minimum threshold for annual volumetric transfers.
609 Overall, *adaptive-cooperative* strategies are more robust relative to *static* strategies under
610 both stochastic and deep uncertainties. Most notable is the drastic improvement in the
611 robustness of the *no transfer* strategy when minimum performance thresholds are placed on
612 donor and recipient basins simultaneously and solely on the donor basin (Figures 5d, e). We
613 have verified these trends with a sensitivity analysis that shows that these results are largely
614 independent of the choice of robustness thresholds (Figure S5).

615

616 Building on the robustness results in Figure 5, we identify which uncertainties control robustness
617 of transfer alternatives using a statistical analysis of the *adaptive-cooperative* strategies (Figure
618 6). We find that uncertainty in long-term precipitation is the main factor that controls whether or
619 not strategies fail, while demand increases play a secondary role for a majority (76/79) of
620 *adaptive-cooperative* strategies. The order of influence of the deeply uncertain factors on
621 strategy failure is: changes in long-term precipitation, total recipient demands, long-term

622 temperature and total donor demands. For 3 (out of 79) *adaptive-cooperative* strategies, changes
623 in total recipient demand is the primary factor controlling strategy failure. Thus, depending upon
624 the specific transfer strategy employed, demand changes in the recipient basin can become more
625 important than climate change in determining strategy success. We find that an increase in long-
626 term precipitation by 10% - 12% of the historical value leads to failure of all *adaptive-*
627 *cooperative* strategies, mainly due to occurrences of flood in either donor or recipient basins or
628 both the basins.

629

630 To illustrate the nature of failures that could confront the INS IBT in the future, we show the
631 temporal variation of deficits and downstream releases for the *adaptive-cooperative* transfer
632 alternative with the highest robustness under stochastic uncertainties under two representative
633 climate and demand change scenarios (Figure 7). The representative climate-demand scenarios
634 combine an increase in long-term demand with a possible decrease (Figure 7a-d) or increase
635 (Figure 7e-h) in long-term precipitation. We find that under decreases in long-term precipitation
636 both reservoirs are likely to face deficits, but in different time periods (Figures 7 a, b). The donor
637 reservoir will be unable to satisfy demands post-monsoon season while the recipient reservoir
638 will face deficits throughout the year. This is expected as the recipient reservoir is already facing
639 deficits during years with low rainfall (Venot et al., 2010; Gaur et al., 2008). Both reservoirs
640 maintain downstream releases much below the flood thresholds in this climate scenario (Figures
641 7 c-d). The situation alters drastically if long-term increases in precipitation occur (Figures 7 e-
642 h). Neither of the reservoirs face deficits under increased rainfall but both face possible flood
643 threshold exceedances during the entire monsoon period. The exceedances occur in throughout
644 the monsoon season (Jun-Sep) for the donor reservoir and late monsoon (Sep-Oct) for the

645 recipient reservoir. This implies that operating strategies will need to react to long-term changes
646 in climate as they start to become evident, instead of relying on historically optimized rules. This
647 presents significant decision analytic challenges regarding choices of time horizons that should
648 be considered for operating strategies, and methods to alter strategies in response to new
649 information regarding the system's evolving climate (Haasnoot et al., 2013; Kwakkel et al.,
650 2016).

651

652 **5. Discussion**

653 Our analysis highlights the complicated decision contexts of IBT megaprojects. We show the
654 utility of well-coordinated and adaptive transfer strategies in managing IBT megaprojects. Such
655 adaptive strategies have not been exploited in prior literature on IBT management. To our
656 knowledge, this is also a first attempt to analyze an IBT megaproject connecting monsoon
657 dominated basins in a developing country where irrigation water forms a major portion of water
658 demand. Although Zhou et al. (2017) show that applying IBTs within an optimization framework
659 can reduce water stress in both the donor and recipient basins, they did not explore the
660 performance of their optimized strategies under long-term changes in demands and climate.
661 Furthermore, their strategy formulation was similar to our *static* formulation, which has been
662 shown to have inferior performance in our analysis both in terms of volume of water transferred
663 as well as in maintaining performance under deep uncertainties.

664

665 In agreement with our findings, other studies on multi-reservoir operation using DPS based
666 strategies show that adaptive strategies are critical to success for well characterized hydro-

667 climatic variability as well as deep uncertainties (Quinn et al., 2017b). Our results highlight that
668 the INS IBT has significant vulnerabilities that even sophisticated transfer strategies may not be
669 able to prevent if long-term precipitation reduces by 10% - 12%. Emanuel et al. (2015) reach a
670 similar conclusion, reporting that water shortage problems may be shared but not completely
671 eliminated if the donor and recipient basins share similar hydro-climatological conditions. Thus,
672 when suggested transfer volumes are quite large, it is nontrivial to reduce water stress in the
673 recipient basin without compromising the demands of donor basin, even when exploiting a state-
674 of-the-art multi-objective decision support framework.

675

676 A key finding of our analysis is that the *no-transfer* strategy emerges as a viable alternative
677 under deeply uncertain futures. Our robustness metric suggests that the status quo of no water
678 transfer might be the better alternative than the INS IBT if the future climate and demands are
679 deeply uncertain. This finding is underlain by assumptions regarding the choice of performance
680 measures that constitute the robustness criterion. Though we show that the estimated robustness
681 values are not sensitive to the selected thresholds of performance measures, it is unclear what
682 happens when we alter the performance measures themselves. For example, reliability is a
683 commonly used metric in water resources literature. By replacing average demand deficit with
684 reliability of demand satisfaction as a satisficing criterion required to achieve robustness (in
685 Table 2), we arrive at considerably different insights on performance of strategies under deeply
686 uncertain futures (Figure S6). Our decision to include the average demand deficit as a robustness
687 criterion was based on its regional relevance. By its own regional standards and a risk attitude
688 represented by a satisficing robustness criterion, the INS IBT will be a worse alternative when
689 compared to the status quo. But by general standards adopted in water resource management

690 literature, the INS IBT may be a better choice. These diverging interpretations indicate the
691 sensitivity of the results to these choices and inclusion of stakeholders in the decision making
692 process to align them to these realities.

693

694 Our analysis, while shedding light on many interesting aspects of IBT megaprojects, lends the
695 way for further investigations. The scope of our analysis did not include social and economic
696 aspects as we formulated the objectives and constraints in the context of volumes of water
697 transferred. However, depending upon the pricing policy, water may have varying economic
698 value in the donor and recipient basins and the desirability of different strategies may change
699 (Lund and Israel, 1995, Draper et al., 2003; Lund et al., 2010). Such an analysis would have to
700 consider not only the present pricing mechanisms but their potential alterations in the future.
701 Furthermore, past literature has shown that a simple cost-benefit analysis may prohibit
702 understanding of complex associations between decision and consequences in such *wicked*
703 problems (Singh et al. 2015). However, economic objectives can be considered as one of the
704 multiple objectives within the MORDM framework to shed light on potential benefits and
705 tradeoffs. It is also important to consider whether the INST IBT will benefit all sections of the
706 society by addressing possible social discrepancies in the use of transferred water
707 (Bandyopadhyay and Perveen, 2004). A detailed stakeholder engagement exercise is a challenge
708 in the study region. The diverse and often undefined stakeholder groups interact in the regional
709 political economy in a complex and uncertain manner. We address this limitation by scoping this
710 study as an exploration of various problem formulations under various exogenous uncertainties
711 and also by testing the sensitivity of strategies against a range of performance variables and
712 thresholds.

713

714 As is true with any modeling exercise, there are several assumptions underlying our system
715 model, choice of performance measures, type and ranges of uncertainties explored, and
716 formulation of decisions. Our system model focused on the INS-IBT but in reality it forms a link
717 in a network of similar projects constituting the NLRP. We considered other water transfers from
718 the donor and recipient reservoirs as external constraints on the system in the form of pre-defined
719 transfers. But these transfers will be simultaneously operated and should ideally be considered as
720 decision variables instead of pre-defined constraints in the model. As the NLRP comprises of 30
721 major water transfers, including all of them simultaneously in a decision framework presents a
722 significant scaling challenge. This issue has also been highlighted by Jain et al. (2005). Another
723 important assumption is the specification of demands. We do not include possible changes in
724 upstream demands that may affect inflows on either reservoir. These changes may be dynamic in
725 nature and complex to capture. We assume that varying the inflows using the stochastic approach
726 and then using a hydrologic model under deeply uncertain futures captures the expected
727 variability in inflows due to other factors not explicitly accounted for. Overall, we want to draw
728 attention to the advantages of the exploratory and iterative problem solving framework presented
729 here. We show that using such a decision framework, decision makers can better understand the
730 consequences of their choices and risk attitudes.

731

732 **6. Conclusion**

733 In this study, we presented a decision analysis framework to discover strategies to transfer water
734 from Godavari to Krishna basin via the INS IBT. We showed the advantages of formulating

735 alternative framings of the same decision problem (*static, adaptive-cooperative* and *adaptive-*
736 *noncooperative*) and explored the role of stochastic and deep uncertainties in prioritizing
737 strategies. We show that transfers can mitigate water stress in the recipient basin, provided they
738 are operated using an adaptive strategy that allows information exchange between the donor and
739 recipient reservoirs. We also find that state-aware adaptive strategies can attain similar
740 performance with much reduced volumes of transfers, when compared to approaches that use an
741 annually fixed rule curve. Finally, changes in the long-term precipitation by 10% - 12% of the
742 historical value significantly degrade the performance of the water transfers. The recipient
743 reservoir faces severe performance degradation in its ability to meet demands under scenarios of
744 reduced long-term precipitation. Similarly, the donor reservoir risks exceeding flood thresholds
745 if long-term precipitation increases.

746

747 Our analysis explores conditions under which IBT megaprojects may be useful alternatives for
748 dealing with water scarcity. Interestingly, the status quo is found to perform better under deeply
749 uncertain changes in future climate and demand suggesting that managing both basins
750 independently could also provide value compared to large scale infrastructure investment.
751 However, we stress that these interpretations are highly dependent on the preferences and risk
752 attitudes of decision makers. We found that although the results are not sensitive to choice of the
753 robustness thresholds, they are quite sensitive to the choice of variables that entail the definition
754 of robustness. This indicates the need for iterative elicitation of priorities and preferences from
755 stakeholders to fine-tune the analysis and enhance its relevance for decision making.
756 Understanding the measures of success of such large scale projects will be challenging and
757 require a co-production of knowledge with various stakeholders. Overall, we provide salient

758 insights for the INS IBT and contribute a generalized methodology for operation of IBTs. Our
759 proposed framework is particularly relevant in developing regions with monsoon dominated
760 rainfall with both basins confronting significant growth in future water demands.

761

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1226 97% in reliability of flood protection and maintaining MEF, respectively. In addition, annual
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1231 optimized strategies from the adaptive (cooperative) formulation using classification and
1232 regression trees (CART). Shown are the ranking of four deeply uncertain factors: changes in
1233 long-term precipitation, temperature, and demands in determining robustness of strategies.
1234 Purple, blue, green and lime green colors represent primary, secondary, tertiary and higher factor
1235 ranking. The CIRCOS plot displays the uncertain factors as the circles outer edge in red and each
1236 optimized strategy is shown on the circle's outer edge in black. A purple line connecting a
1237 strategy to a factor indicates that factor being the primary control on strategy failure under
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1240 Figure 7. Relative demand deficits and downstream releases in donor and recipient reservoirs
1241 under two deeply uncertain scenarios with increase and decrease in long-term
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1243 10% increase in long-term annual demands in both basins. (e,f,g,h)Scenario with 42% increase in
1244 long-term precipitation combined with a 10% increase in long-term annual demands in both
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1246 the variation of demand deficits and releases across 15-years of the planning horizon. Relative

1247 demand deficits are estimated by dividing the volumetric deficit with the total annual demand in
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Characteristic	Donor	Recipient
Gauge station	Perur	Nagarjuna Sagar
Average annual flow	77,017 Mm ³	29,625 Mm ³
Irrigated area	121,500 ha	1,182,200 ha
Annual demand	603 Mm ³	8,535 Mm ³
Reservoir	Inchampalli (proposed)	Nagarjuna Sagar (existing)
Storage capacity	4285 Mm ³	5733 Mm ³
Catchment area	269,000 km ²	220,705 km ²

1353 Table 1: Water availability and demands in the donor and recipient basins

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Formulation	Description	Optimization
No water transfer	<p>This represents the status-quo where both basins manage their water resources independently, thus no water transfer occurs from the donor to the recipient reservoir. We, however, assume the existence of the proposed reservoir in the donor basin and consider the demands from pre-defined transfers on both reservoirs. It is quite likely that the donor basin manages the proposed reservoir to increase its own water security.</p> <p>Additionally, considering pre-defined transfers allows us to incorporate demand growth in regions of Southern India that are or will be dependent on the donor or recipient basins in the future.</p>	No
Proposed transfer	<p>This represents the operative strategy defined by the regional authorities. Recall that these volumes are specified deterministically by analyzing the monthly inflows and demands at the donor site, considering only historical observations (NWDA, 2020).</p>	No
Static water transfers (<i>static</i>)	<p>The static formulation mimics the proposed formulation but maximizes its performance by optimizing it. This ‘open loop control’ prescribes a sequence of actions regardless of the current SOW (Equation 1). We assume that the same strategy</p>	Yes

	will be implemented every year.	
Adaptive-cooperative water transfers	In this ‘closed loop control’, decision variables are determined by a state-aware adaptive rule. We condition the decision to transfer water on storage and demand states of donor and recipient reservoirs (see also section 3.1.1).	Yes
Adaptive-noncooperative transfers	This formulation is similar to adaptive-cooperative formulation except that the transfer volumes are conditioned only on the storage and demand states of the donor reservoir (see also section 3.1.1). This formulation was developed to understand the role of information sharing between donor and recipient reservoirs.	Yes

1363 Table 2: Five different problem formulations to identify candidate water transfer strategies

1364 for the INS IBT.

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Objective	Definition	Description	Units	Range
Demand Reliability (J_{rel})	$\frac{1}{NR} \sum_{j=1}^{NR} \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{N_j} DM_{t,j}}{N_j} \right)$ <p>Reliability is defined as the probability that the system is in a satisfactory state</p>	$DM_{t,j} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (d_{t,j} < ad_{t,j}) \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$ <p>$d_{t,j}$ is the demand satisfied at time t for realisation j</p> <p>$ad_{t,j}$ is the actual demand at time t for realisation j</p> <p>N_j is the total number time of periods for realisation j</p> <p>NR is the total number of realizations</p>	[%]	[0, 100]
Demand Resilience (J_{res})	$\frac{1}{NR} \sum_{j=1}^{NR} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{M_j} T_{i,j}}{M_j}$ <p>Resilience quantifies how quickly a system recovers from failure</p>	<p>$T_{i,j}$ is the duration of i^{th} failure event for realisation j</p> <p>M_j is the total number of failure events for realisation j</p>	[days]	[0, ∞]
Demand Vulnerability (J_{vul})	$\frac{1}{NR} \sum_{j=1}^{NR} \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{N_j} (ad_{t,j} - d_{t,j})}{\sum_{t=1}^{N_j} DM_{t,j} \times \sum_{t=1}^{N_j} ad_{t,j}}$ <p>Vulnerability quantifies the</p>		[%]	[0, ∞]

	magnitude of failure			
Environmental flow reliability (J_{EF})	$\frac{1}{NR} \sum_{j=1}^{NR} \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{N_j} EF_{t,j}}{N_j} \right) \times 100$	$EF_{t,j} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (ef_{t,j} < mef_t) \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$ <p>$ef_{t,j}$ is the actual flow released as environmental flow at time t for realisation j</p> <p>mef_t is the minimum environmental flow at time t (minimum environmental flows based on Smakhtin, 2006)</p>	[%]	[0, 100]
Flood Reliability (J_{flood})	$\frac{1}{NR} \sum_{j=1}^{NR} \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{N_j} F_{t,j}}{N_j} \right) \times 100$	$F_{t,j} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (r_{t,j} > ft_t) \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$ <p>$r_{t,j}$ are the actual releases to downstream at time t for realisation j</p> <p>ft_t are the flood thresholds at time t (Supplementary Material S4)</p>	[%]	[0, 100]
Constraints				
Environmental flow	$J_{EF} > 80$		[%]	[0, 100]

reliability			
Predefined transfer reliability (J_{PT})	$J_{PT} = \frac{1}{NR} \sum_{j=1}^{NR} \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{N_j} P_{t,j}}{N} \right) \times 100; P_{t,j} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } (pt_{tj} < apt_t) \\ 0 & \text{else} \end{cases}$ <p>$J_{PT} > 80$, where</p> <p>pt_{tj} is the predefined transfer satisfied at time t</p> <p>apt_t is the actual predefined transfer at time t</p>	[%]	[0, 100]

1372 Table 3. Definitions of objective functions and constraints of the decision problem for IBT.

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Performance measure [unit]	Range explored for sensitivity analysis
Average demand deficit [Mm ³]	10 Mm ³ – 30 Mm ³
Reliability of maintaining minimum environmental flows [%]	80% - 97%
Reliability of flood protection [%]	80% - 97%
Mean annual transfer volume [%]	30% - 70% of annual proposed transfer volume

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1384 sensitivity analysis.

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